

“Content” as infrastructure - reflections on Jisc's support for the Digital Humanities

Digital Humanities congress, University of Sheffield, 4-5 September 2024

In this presentation we'll cover:

- A bit about us
- Why “content” as infrastructure?
- Looking back and looking forward: what is Jisc?
- Where we've been and where we are: highlights
- Some reflections (and challenges)
- Your reflections on the value of Jisc
- An invitation

About us: 40 years+ experience of strategies for research content

Paola Marchionni, Head of engagement (content and discovery), Jisc

Peter Findlay, subject matter specialist, digital scholarship, Jisc

Jisc Digital Resources activities

We work across teams to support our members with

- Content and discovery services
- UKRI support for OA monographs
- Research management
- Open research
- National content agreements with the “big 5”
- Controlled Digital Lending
- Institutional Rights Retention Policies (IRRP)
- Shared discovery services: Library Hub and Archives Hub
- Digital preservation
- Digital transformation

Why “Content” as infrastructure?

Digital collections for (Digital) Humanities

Digital collections have become fundamental to modern scholarship.

[The Impacts of Digital Collections](#) (2015), Eric T. Meyer and Kathryn Eccles

Content in a networked age

Electronic information might be considered as being in states

Information **at rest** (in electronic storage (drives or cloud))

Information **in use** (accessed, processed, transformed)

Information **in transit** (between hosts)

[The three states of information | The University of Edinburgh \(archive.org\)](#)

And content?

Content '**contained**' in **carriers & systems** (analogue/digital)

Content **portable & transformable** (fluid, open)

Content **as data** (digital & networked)

CC BY-SA 3.0

“Content” life cycle – we know it well but...

Some elements have had much more attention than **others**

- Creation
- Access
- **Discovery**
- **IPR**
- Tools
- Skills
- Analysis at scale
- Standards
- **Preservation**
- **Sustainability (including business models)**

Jisc (“content”) infrastructure

CONTENT AS DATA

SERVICES

ADVICE AND
GUIDANCE

COLLABORATIONS

COMMUNITY
BUILDING

R&D AND
INNOVATION

FUNDING

Looking back and looking forward: what is Jisc?

Mission

We're on a mission to improve lives through the digital transformation of education and research.

What we do

Crucial services, eg Janet Network – the UK's National research and education network (NREN)

Save sector time and money

Trusted expert advice, guidance, building communities

In numbers

1250

Staff

359

FE and skills providers

164

HE institutions

24

Research members

Our impact

For every £1 members
invest in Jisc, they receive
£3 in savings

94% members see Jisc
as their trusted partner

96% compliance with UKRI OA
policy thanks to OA agreements
with 65 publishers

509 DDoS attacks to
92 members
mitigated

Where the money comes from

Funded by UK HE and
FE funding bodies and
member subscriptions

We provide critical services in...

Cloud

Connectivity and
cyber security

Content and
discovery

Data analytics

Licensing

Research
management

Student
experience

Verification
services

We've been around for a while

1 Apr 1993: Follet
review established JISC
- the Joint Information
Systems Committee

The electronic library programme (eLib)

ukoln.ac.uk/services/elib/background/history.html

Page Content blog login Digi blog Intranet My Drive My team - Power BI Sharepoint Roadmunk Concur HR system >> All Bookmarks

Introduction

For many years now there have been predictions about evolution of the *electronic* or *virtual* library: a library without books. There have been as many predictions about how this will occur and who will run it, as there have been about what form it will take. Libraries everywhere are feeling the effects of new, rapidly advancing network technology, and find themselves caught in a whirlwind of commercial and technological forces claiming to provide the *right solutions* for dealing with electronic information. How will libraries survive this confusion? How can libraries best support and advance their universities into the 21st century?

Background

It was questions like these that saw the commissioning of the [Libraries Review](#) by the UK Higher Education Funding Councils, chaired by Professor Sir Brian Follett in 1993. As a direct response to the Libraries Review, the Joint Information Systems Committee (JISC) established the Electronic Libraries Programme (eLib). The programme has a budget of 15 million pounds over 3 years to fund projects in a variety of programme areas. The main aim of the eLib programme, through its projects, is to engage the Higher Education community in developing and shaping the implementation of the electronic library.

The programme has been established through two separate calls for proposals that have so far yielded almost 60 projects funded in different programme areas. These areas are:

- Document Delivery
- Access To Network Resources
- Training and Awareness
- Electronic Journals
- Digitisation
- Images
- Electronic Short Loan Collections
- On Demand Publishing
- Pre-Prints and Grey Literature
- Supporting Studies
- Quality Assurance

The Programme has also funded the Higher Education Digitisation Service at the University of Hertfordshire.

<https://www.ukoln.ac.uk/services/elib/background/history.html>

All change in 2012 JISC becomes Jisc

~~JISC~~

2011 Wilson review - report to HEFCE by the JISC Review Group

...[Jisc] has played a pivotal role in the UK as an enabler of innovation and of early, widespread adoption of information and communications technology (ICT) ...

- ... In an era of financial constraint, it is necessary to refocus activities [...] and to ensure JISC operates with a sustainable financial model...*

Evolving role but still supporting digital transformation

1993

Administrative /
biographical
background:

The Joint Information Systems Committee (JISC) was established on 1 April 1993. Its role is to support post-16 and higher education and research by providing leadership in the use of information and communications technology) in support of learning, teaching, research and administration. It is funded by the Higher Education Funding Council for England, the Scottish Higher Education Funding Council, the Higher Education Funding Council for Wales and the Department of Education Northern Ireland.

2024

About us

[Our vision](#) is for the UK to be a world leader in technology for education, research and innovation.

We're on a mission to improve lives through the digital transformation of education and research. That's why we exist. It's what drives us every day.

Where we've been and where we are: highlights

- Transformational content
- Innovation and experimentation
- Building communities
- Delivering efficiencies

(1) Transformational content

Pioneering programmes

JISC has done outstanding work to create and collect electronic content and resources, and in negotiating collective procurement on behalf of the sectors. There is no comparable body within the UK, and internationally its reputation is outstanding as a strategic leader and partner.

HEFCE Review, 2011

Skills, strategy and infrastructure

89% said project allowed inst to increase capacity and infrastructure to create and sustain digitised content

The slide features the JISC logo in the top left and the text 'eContent programme' in the top right. The main content is a list of bullet points describing the programme's achievements and goals. On the right side, there is a screenshot of the 'JISC content' website interface, which includes a category selection dropdown menu set to 'History and politics' and a preview of a digital document titled '19th Century British Pamphlets Online'.

- Since 2004: nearly £30m and almost 80 projects
- Investment in high quality digital content for research, teaching and learning through:
 - digitisation; enriching existing collections; clustering content; user generated content/community engagement; developing skills and strategies
- New eContent programme, £5.4m Nov 2011:
 - a) Digitisation for Open Educational Resources
 - b) Large scale digitisation
 - c) Clustering content
- See JISC funded content and download the JISC content widget at www.jisc-content.ac.uk

08/09/2011 ALTC2011, University of Leeds slide 1

Democratising access across UK HEIs

JISC Collections, one of the unsung heroes of the digital humanities, which has done miraculous work in negotiating digital licences over the years which enable British universities of all shapes, sizes and budgets to purchase a wide range of digital resources...

[What Price Gale Cengage?](#) Andrew Prescott (2016)

EEBO

25
commercial
Publishers'
archives
licensed

ECCO

£18m
Savings to
HEIs over
10 years

A strategic national approach

Transformational digital content and resources support the broader government agenda to build Digital Britain and open up data for the twenty-first century.

Digitising Britain for our Digital Futures

Vision: a sustainable national content collection of compelling rich and accessible digitised resources for excellence in research, learning and teaching.

"I want to make Britain the most connected, the most wired up, the most digitally advanced country there can be."
David Cameron, Prime Minister

[Inspiring Research, Inspiring Scholarship](#), Simon Tanner and Marilyn Deegan (2010)

Embedded in research and scholarship

British Library digitised newspapers
(2004-2007)

Foundational digitised
resources, used in
Living w Machines

The Great War Archive (2008)
Old Weather (2010)

The image is a composite for the 'Old Weather' project. On the left is a black and white photograph of a soldier in a military uniform. In the center is a snippet of a handwritten log entry with cursive text. On the right is a dark poster for 'Old Weather' with the title in large white letters. Below the title, it says 'Help scientists transcribe Arctic and worldwide weather observations recorded in ship's logs since the mid-19th century.' There are three orange buttons: 'Old Weather: WWII' with the subtext 'Recover hidden weather data collected by the Navy during World War II', 'Old Weather: Whaling' with 'Explore the Arctic of the past from the deck of a whaling ship', and 'Old Weather: Arctic' with 'Rediscover the historic Arctic voyages of the U.S. Navy and Coast Guard'. A URL 'http://www.oucs.ox.ac.uk/www1lit' is at the bottom left.

Community collections
and citizen science
precursors

Early English Books Online (EEBO)

Seminal nationally
licensed resources
embedded in research
and the classroom

(2) Innovation and experimentation

Digging into Data (DiD): transatlantic partnership

Controlled vocabularies, schemas and linked data

Who

Lieut. Col. James; Capt. Craig. Col Craig; Sir James Craig; Viscount Craigavon

What

1141 contributions to debates at Westminster; 1163 at Stormont ; Treasurer Royal Household; Parliamentary Secretary; Prime Minister of Northern Ireland; Member of Parliament

When

Westminster offices held: 1916; 1919; 1920;
Stormont offices held: 1921-1940

Where

Westminster; Stormont; Down East; Down Mid

DiD: Imaginary lenses for visualising text corpora

Collections Data could enable new forms of research

- disseminative ('this is') – presentational aids for dissemination
- operational ('what?') – enable intuitive and speedy observation of captured data
- analytical ('why?') – investigative, can be used to examine complex relationships
- inventive ('how?') – aid improving existing models, methods etc

“A project (2014) to explore new visualization techniques for use in large scale linguistic and literary corpora using the collections of the British National Corpus and various smaller archives of poetry.”

[Digital Humanities @ Oxford](#)

Linked Data but also linked people

...it's worth saying that Jisc has been really important in my own research career. In fact, it was a first funder of the Pelagios project....

*...the other thing that was genuinely a great value within that programme was that all of the projects that it supported **were required to cooperate with one another**, keep each other informed, there were **regular meetups** and that was really effective and important for us*

...

Leif Isaksen, [Is AI for me? Jisc podcast](#), 2023

Taking the long view: trends in the landscape

Discussing AI and data trends with our members and partners

Information – we should focus on providing **fundamental information** which is tailored to the **context of where people are operating**.

Provide it to the **digitally obliged** (those having to provide services) and the **digitally curious** (those with an interest)

[Is AI for Me report Jisc 2022](#)

Output: 6 podcasts to explore what the impacts of AI might be on humanities research and what is needed to better support them in an age where if it not data it will become less and less relevant.

(3) Building communities, the human infrastructure

Collectively working for change

Testing the ground together

We don't have the answers, but you might have them or someone else might. Together we **explore challenges**, share **knowledge and resources**. We then open up **dialogue**, **gather and redistribute insights** and help **develop innovative ideas**.

Livework © 2017 www.liveworkstudio.com London Oslo Rotterdam São Paulo 21 November 2017

Get involved > Institutional rights retention policies task and finish group

Search Jisc

Institutional rights retention policies task and finish group

We have convened the institutional rights retention policies task and finish group (T&FG) to guide the implementation of the first stage of a project aiming to support, and accelerate, the implementation of IRRPs within our HE member institutions.

Supporting skills development through collaboration

7 tutorials: computational analysis of large-scale digital collections

Maximise impact through collaborations where there are existing channels and communities

Supporting knowledge sharing across GLAMA sectors

[DCDC2025](#) – 29-31 July, Durham University and online

The many different speakers and sessions have opened up new ways of thinking about what we do and how we do it, while recognising our different contexts, and the limitations and uncertainty that lies ahead.

DCDC2021 Delegate

(4) Delivering efficiencies

Testing new business models for digitisation

- 2022: Collaboration between Jisc, Wiley, BAAS and 14 universities
- 1m pages on the history of science digitised and delivered through Wiley infrastructure
- free to UK and on open access after 10 years
- UK Medical Heritage Library (2014-17) Jisc, Wellcome, 9 HEIs and the Internet Archive digitise millions of pages of 19th century medical books

The image shows two overlapping website screenshots. The top screenshot is from the British Association for the Advancement of Science (BAAS) website, featuring the text: "British Association for the Advancement of Science - Collections on the history of science 1830s-1970s" and "Nearly 1 million pages of digitised texts from the British Association for the Advancement of Science (BAAS) and participating UK universities." Below this is a historical map of Bristol. The bottom screenshot is from the UK Medical Heritage Library website, showing the header "MEDICAL HERITAGE LIBRARY" with the tagline "opening access to seven centuries of medical history" and a navigation menu with items: "About", "Search Our Collections", "Blog", "Collaborate", and "Content". Below the menu is a list of "Primary Source Sets" including "Anti-Black Racism in Medicine", "Disability", "Disability, Music Technology, and Education", "Disability and Technology", "LGBTQUIA+", and "Vaccines". To the right of the list is a section titled "UK Medical Heritage Library" with a paragraph of text: "The UK Medical Heritage Library brings together books and pamphlets from 10 research libraries in the UK, focused on the 19th and early 20th century history of medicine and related disciplines. This ongoing digitisation project is funded by Jisc (http://www.jisc-content.ac.uk/) and the Wellcome Library (http://wellcomelibrary.org). The UK Medical Heritage Library is a sub-set of the Medical Heritage Library (archive.org/details/medicalheritagelibrary)." An anatomical illustration of a human arm and skull is visible on the right side of the screenshot.

But difficult to scale, resource, replicate, identify and aligning priorities (with publishers)...

Lowering the cost of purchasing digital archives

- Agreement with commercial publishers
- Collective discounts
- Transparent one-off charges
- Clear T&Cs (eg TDM access)
- Over £1m saved to libraries in 5 years

Digital archival collections group purchasing scheme

Collectively lowering the cost of acquiring digital archival collections.

[Browse the licence subscriptions manager catalogue](#)

Faster procurement for Digital Preservation

- Pre-qualified vendors
- Faster procurement time
- Compliant process
- Conforms to sector standards
- Advice and support
- Get best value

Digital preservation systems dynamic purchasing system (DPS)

Save time and effort with an easy, fast and compliant route to acquiring a digital preservation system to suit your organisation's needs.

Get in touch

Some reflections (and challenges)

(1) How far have we progressed?

A lot has changed but some fundamental issues are as relevant today as they were years ago

2008

“address IPR issues meticulously (clearance)”

“standards of all kinds, particularly metadata”

“accessibility issues”

“promotion and dissemination of the collection (sustainability)”

[Large-scale digitisation: the £22 million JISC programme and the role of libraries, J Sykes 2008](#)

2023

“manual clearance as potentially containing in-copyright material”

“how to use digitised collections and metadata”

“different accessibility requirements”

“promoting their [outputs] re-use and adaptation”

[Collaborative Historical Research in the Age of Big Data, R. Ahnert et al, 2023](#)

(2) How do we maximise learning?

Cascading and retaining sector memory can be a challenge

There is a perceived lack of impact and effectiveness from digital cultural heritage projects... Concerns were raised regarding the repetitive nature of discussions and the limited lasting tangible results from past digital collections and infrastructure projects. There is a strong desire for knowledge sharing across the sector. Establishing open communication channels for sharing best practices and tangible outcomes, along with mechanisms for tracking and assessing impact, is essential.

[TaNC User Research: UK Gallery, Library, Archive and Museum \(GLAM\) Digital Collections Infrastructure](#), Bailey-Ross, Claire et al, 2024

(2) How do we maximise learning?

Huge amount of collective knowledge built up over the years

But things get in the way: cyclical nature of conversations, people moving on and new people joining in, changing priorities, unstable funding landscape...

We're keen to collaborate to support and improve knowledge sharing.

[Strategic Content Alliance 2007-2014](#)

(3) Renewed advocacy for the (Digital) Humanities?

DH is well embedded...

Pidd ... noted that ... “most DH no longer stands as a domain that needs special consideration by funders.” it should just be considered another part of arts and humanities research.

This led panellists to note that, rather than advocacy for DH, what was needed in the UK was advocacy for the arts and humanities more broadly.

[Communicating the value and impact of DH in teaching, research and infrastructure](#), UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Network, 2021)

The screenshot shows a search interface with a search bar containing 'Digital Humanities'. Below the search bar, there are filter options and a results table. The results table has three columns: Name, University affiliation(s), and General type. The first result is 'Digital Humanities Centre, Lancaster' at Lancaster University, categorized as 'University-based infrastructure'. The second result is 'Digital Humanities and Sensory Heritage Network' at the University of Oxford, also categorized as 'University-based infrastructure'. A red circle highlights the text 'Showing 1 to 30 of 160 infrastructure(s) found'.

Name	University affiliation(s)	General type
Digital Humanities Centre, Lancaster	Lancaster University	University-based infrastructure
Digital Humanities and Sensory Heritage Network	University of Oxford, University of Oxford	University-based infrastructure

<https://www.humanities.org.uk>

(3) Renewed advocacy for the (Digital) Humanities?

But constantly under treat

The arts and humanities are declining in the portfolios of funders and challenged by wider governmental policies. This requires a rethink of DH...

[Communicating the value and impact of DH in teaching, research and infrastructure](#), UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Network, 2021

Arts and Humanities Research Council funding 'has been some sort of oasis, but it too is now quickly drying up'

[Times Higher Education](#), Jack Grove, 2023

Cyber and student recruitment are clearly critical

AI is a common challenge but not the single most important challenge in comparison to others.

%	Most cited challenges	%	Top single challenge
49%	Cyber security	12%	Cyber security
47%	Artificial intelligence	12%	Student recruitment (international)
35%	Student recruitment (international)	10%	Student recruitment (domestic)
33%	Escalating costs	9%	Escalating costs
27%	Student recruitment (domestic)	9%	Business system improvement
27%	Student experience	6%	IT infrastructure (including hardware, software, cloud)
23%	Digital capability and skills	5%	Artificial intelligence
22%	IT infrastructure (including hardware, software, cloud)	4%	Learning spaces, physical and virtual
22%	Business system improvement	4%	Student experience
22%	Data and business intelligence	3%	Staff recruitment and retention, Data and business intelligence, Assessment and feedback, Digital leadership and

Jisc leadership survey 2024

(4) AI: friend or foe? Or is it about something else?

How can we influence AI's development to support DH with data?

*It's about staring hard at data and making library **catalogues into data** so you can stare hard at them.*

*[Macroscopes & Microscopes: Scholar Cyborgs in the Digital Research Library](#),
Tim Hitchcock RLUK 2019*

*Libraries support individuals working through the many facets of complexity that constitute the human condition. The collections as **data conversation** is an extension of this tradition - provision of the means for meaning making.*

[On a Collections as Data Imperative](#), Thomas Padilla, LOC Labs

[Webinar Blog Post: AI ready library collections; the practicalities](#)

Communities' reflections on the value of Jisc

This is what some of you said...

...something about holding a **space** in which these discussions can happen... building up a **network of people**...

Melissa Terras

...to help people **pick their way through**, not just a complex landscape, but one that's changing so rapidly...
...a really important **convening and brokering** role as well. Jisc is so well connected to different **sectors**, particularly the galleries, libraries, archives and museums sector and helping universities, librarians, information professionals to connect.

Jane Winters

...and this...

...well-positioned to take the **long view** to not get too swept up by the now, by the hype, ... to try and think about the kind of **infrastructures** at a kind of **socio technical level** that the humanities are going to need...

James Baker

...a mass effort is required at the moment to make sure that people aren't **reinventing the wheel**, that they can use things that have already been developed ... to get from digitised collections to collections data...
So yeah, I think it's a rationalisation process... it's **connecting what is out there** and it's on all of us, but I think Jisc is in a really fantastic position to help with that...

Ruth Ahnert

Invitation!

Work with us

- If you have an interest in SLMs and RAG, we want to hear from you, let us know what you think we should be pursuing, refine requirements....
- We are likely to have an advisory group, focus groups, interviews so you can contribute in various ways
- Keep an eye on our [Content and Digitisation](#) and [Digital Research](#) blogs

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Thank You!

*We welcome
your questions or
comments*